

WORK MOTIVATION FRAMEWORK OF THE NON-TENURED TEACHERS**Cydeah Aldic J. Conchas¹****Prince Hope Cordova²****Jesenex Jacob L. Malabago³****Juber Ann R. Rivera⁴****Jestoni C. Siarot⁵****Catherine O. Ureta⁶**

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the dimensions of work motivation among non-tenured teachers. The study employed and made use of the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) as the research design. This was conducted to 150 non-tenured teachers in Davao del Sur through a non-experimental qualitative survey questionnaire.

The findings of the study revealed five dimensions of the work motivation framework of non-tenured teachers. These are: Job Fulfillment and Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Challenges and Influences, Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability, and Student Behavior and Workload.

Keywords:

Non-tenured teachers, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, job fulfillment, workload, job satisfaction, resource availability

INTRODUCTION

Work motivation for employees in an organization or institution can increase their productivity and make their perception more responsive to their work environment (Niati et al., 2021). The work motivation framework for non-tenured teachers will be the basis of how these employees work in a way that the purpose of efficiently and effectively can be achieved in several important factors that affect the motivation through their personal needs, goals, and perceptions and how to fulfill these (Priyono; et al., 2016).

The driving force behind some work-related actions that affect people's job satisfaction and general well-being is known as work motivation. The Merriam-Webster dictionary defines work motivation as the act or process of providing someone with a purpose to do something. It stands for a power or influence that drives someone to behave. These broad definitions of motivation highlight how vital they inspire people to act. It involves different factors encouraging commitment and interest in completing tasks and achieving goals. According to Galindo (2024), motivation can arise from intrinsic factors, such as the sense of fulfillment gained from completing tasks, and extrinsic factors, such as monetary rewards.

Researchers categorize motivation into two types: extrinsic and intrinsic. Grand Canyon University (2024) explains that external factors, including positive and negative reinforcement, drive extrinsic motivation. These motivations can include salary, material benefits, vacations, and rewards. Teachers may feel motivated by how well they perceive their work is compensated. For example, they often pursue professional development or further their education to advance on the pay scale. External incentives like fair salary, job security, and performance reviews impact their extrinsic motivation.

In contrast, intrinsic motivation stems from a genuine interest and enjoyment in the work. It arises from feelings, desires, and personal values, all shaped by an individual's behavior and what matters to them. Researchers often call intrinsic motivation 'internal interest'. For teachers, intrinsic motivation comes from their passion for teaching and learning as they strive for personal growth and success in the classroom. Moreover, Grand Canyon University (2024) emphasizes that motivation is vital in balancing the external pressures of work instability, salary, and recognition with the intrinsic passion for teaching. In the article of Vo et al. (2022), motivation is vital for employees or, for this subject, non-tenured teachers, as it directly impacts their work engagement, work

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satisfaction, and overall performance. Schools can assist non-tenured instructors in overcoming obstacles like employment insecurity and dependence on outside rewards by encouraging motivation.

This research was conducted to explore the work motivation framework of non-tenured teachers, investigating whether intrinsic or extrinsic factors primarily drive their motivation. Gaining insight into this dynamic could answer the questions surrounding their work experiences and challenges.

OBJECTIVES

The study was conducted to determine the dimensions of the work motivation framework of non-tenured teachers. The work motivation framework would serve as the basis to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these professionals perform their daily tasks effectively and efficiently despite their work status.

METHODOLOGY

Non-experimental quantitative research using the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) test measured the adequacy of factor analysis of the dataset collected and the correlation of the underlying factors. In the KMO test, the factors are extracted when the value is closer to 1.000, which indicates a more suitable sample for factor analysis. This also suggests that the variables share enough common variance. Bartlett's sphericity test gives the dataset's suitability for dimensionality reduction techniques. The eigenvalues of the factors in descending order against the number of factors were graphically represented in a Scree Plot to determine the optimal number of factors to retain.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section encompasses the analysis and interpretation of data. The chapter dives into the results and findings of the study, utilizing the statistical software SPSS, where KMO and Bartlett's Test are applied.

KMO and Bartlett's Test. The collected data was analyzed using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Table 1 shows the analysis of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's test of Sphericity used to determine whether the data is suitable for factor analysis.

These tests help confirm that exploratory factor analysis (EFA) or principal component analysis (PCA) can reveal meaningful insights into variable structures. For instance, high KMO values and significant Bartlett's tests were pivotal in studies examining student satisfaction surveys and organizational behavior metrics (Zhao et al., 2019; Ledesma & Valero-Mora, 2007).

The result obtained from the KMO measure of sample adequacy provided a value of 0.826, indicating that the sampling is meritorious. This implies a substantial overlap in the degree of information among the variables and a robust partial correlation. Accepting values greater than 0.600 is barely acceptable, according to Kaiser (1974), which suggests that additional data collection is optional for factor analysis.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.826
Approx. Chi-Square		3715.832
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	435
	Sig.	.000

Table 1. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Furthermore, the presence of underlying factors is also supported by a chi-square value of 3715.832, a degree of freedom (df) value of 435, and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) derived from Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, which shows that the correlation matrix differs significantly from the identity matrix. This confirms that the sample used is appropriate for the study and that factor analysis is a suitable treatment as an analytical tool. Overall, the outcome shows that the study's sampling size is adequate for proceeding on to factor analysis.

In Table 2, the exploratory factor analysis conducted on the dataset identified five factors with corresponding eigenvalues of 12.148, 2.795, 2.238, 1.353, and 1.323. Eigenvalues represent the total amount of variance that the identified factors can explain. These values provide insight into how well the factors capture the underlying

patterns of variation in the data and serve as an essential metric for evaluating the goodness of fit of the EFA model (Yong & Pearce, 2013).

Table 2. Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.148	40.494	40.494	12.148	40.494	40.494	7.788	25.961	25.961
2	2.795	9.318	49.812	2.795	9.318	49.812	5.876	19.585	45.547
3	2.238	7.461	57.273	2.238	7.461	57.273	2.666	8.885	54.432
4	1.353	4.510	61.783	1.353	4.510	61.783	1.950	6.501	60.932
5	1.323	4.409	66.192	1.323	4.409	66.192	1.578	5.259	66.192

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

By examining the variance percentages in the Total Variance Explained, we can observe that the first factor explains 25.961% of the total variance, indicating that it accounts for a significant portion of the variability in the dataset. The second factor explains 19.585% of the variance, the third factor explains 8.885% of the variance, the fourth factor explains 6.501%, and the fifth factor explains 5.259%. Therefore, the first factor contributes the most to explaining the variance, while the fifth factor has the most minor impact.

The five factors collectively account for 66.192% of the total variance, as indicated in the table. This means that these five factors capture most of the underlying variation of the dataset, providing a meaningful representation of the data's structure.

Rotated Component Matrix with the 28 attributes. As presented, there are thirty items categorized into five dimensions. The table shows that two items were not included in categorizing five dimensions. These items have faced validity issues and low commonalities and were removed from the model. This is supported by Clark and Watson (2019), who suggested that items with face validity issues can distort the interpretability of factors, reducing the overall credibility of the analysis. Modern research in psychometrics stresses the importance of rigorous pre-testing and pilot studies to identify potential problematic items early.

Meanwhile, the Scree Plot was used to illustrate the total variance, and Eigenvalues were plotted against all factors in a graphical manner. This determines the number of constructs that motivated the non-tenured teachers to stay motivated in their jobs.

Figure 1 shows how valuable the scree plot is for figuring out how many hidden items are best to keep in the analysis. Eigenvalues indicate the presence of five (5) different components in the analysis with a coefficient of one or above (Yong & Pearce, 2013).

Figure 1. The Scree plot

This study aimed to develop a framework based on the motivation dimensions of non-tenured teachers. Using Exploratory Factor Analysis, five dimensions were extracted from the data collected through a 30-item survey questionnaire given to the study's respondents.

Job Fulfilment and Motivation. Table 3 shows the attributes grouped as “Job Fulfillment and Motivation,” which indicates the individual's intrinsic motivation and experience. The data show that the participants rated Item 2 scores 0.809, indicating that daily job enjoyment strongly predicts overall job satisfaction and motivation. Dinham and Scott (2000). Item 9 scores 0.733, which shows that professional growth opportunities are significant motivators. Item 3 scores of 0.730 reflect that a sense of purpose in teaching contributes strongly to satisfaction (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Item 4 scores of 0.717 suggest that administrative support is crucial to job satisfaction. Item 8 scores 0.716 highlight the importance of development opportunities for non-tenured teachers. Item 17 scores 0.715, indicating that positive experiences within the school boost motivation. Item 16 scores 0.686, suggesting that performance motivation contributes to overall satisfaction.

Item 19 scores 0.683 points to the importance of work-life balance and its moderate impact on job satisfaction—item 29 scores 0.672, reflecting the significance of holistic engagement in the teaching role. Item 5 scores 0.660, shows the effects of leadership support on teacher satisfaction. Item 28 scores 0.597 indicating that while fulfillment from teaching is important, it is a slightly less influential factor compared to others. Item 25 scores 0.561 shows that a sense of responsibility, while valuable, has a relatively lower impact on overall job satisfaction.

The responses to the questions in this table highlight the strong connection between job fulfillment and motivation. Many non-tenured teachers are driven by a genuine passion for teaching, which boosts their professional growth and classroom engagement. Teachers who are deeply committed to students' academic success and personal development demonstrate intrinsic motivation.

Dinham and Scott (2000) discovered that the "intrinsic" benefits of teaching specifically, those associated with student and instructor accomplishment, are the main sources of happiness for teachers. The study aligns with Ryan and Deci's (2000) work on intrinsic motivation, highlighting how internal fulfillment comes from engaging in an activity; personal satisfaction and intrinsic rewards are central to fulfilling psychological needs and enhancing overall well-being. Whether in the classroom or in more general psychological contexts, both studies emphasize the significance of internal elements in promoting motivation and satisfaction.

Table 3: Rotated component matrix with group attributes of Job Fulfillment and Motivation

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
Item 2	I enjoy my daily teaching responsibilities.	0.809	Job Fulfillment and Motivation
Item 9	I feel motivated to stay in this profession due to the development opportunities provided.	0.733	
Item 3	I feel that my job contributes meaningfully to the student's learning.	0.730	
Item 4	I receive adequate support from the school administration.	0.717	
Item 8	The school provides support for non-tenured teachers to improve their teaching skills.	0.716	
Item 17	I feel that my work motivation has increased since joining the school.	0.715	
Item 16	I am motivated to perform well in my teaching job.	0.686	
Item 19	My institution provides me with mental breaks within a month	0.683	
Item 29	I find joy in mentoring or guiding students outside of academic lessons (e.g, life skills, personal growth)	0.672	
Item 5	The school leadership is responsive to the concerns of non-tenured teachers.	0.660	
Item 28	Teaching is fulfilling even without rewards	0.597	
Item 25	I feel a deep sense of responsibility to help my students succeed	0.561	

Job Satisfaction. Table 4 shows the seven items under Job Satisfaction, indicating that *I am satisfied with my current salary* and have the highest factor score of 0.873. In contrast, non-tenured teachers are satisfied with their current salary. Item 13 states that the organization determines the compensation based on the experience and contribution of teaching, with a factor score of 0.851. Item 14, with a factor of 0.849, represents the benefit package received that meets the needs of every non-tenured teacher. Item 12, with a factor score of 0.753, shows that the job demands are reasonable enough. Item 18 shows the tendency to receive tenure influences motivation at work with a factor score of 0.609. Item no. 1 shows that every non-tenured teacher is satisfied with their current teaching position. Lastly, in item no 10, with a factor score of 0.546, non-tenured teachers are motivated to stay in the profession because of the development opportunities provided in an organization.

Job satisfaction arises from a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic motivators. However, this table shows that extrinsic factors like compensation, recognition, and career advancement are vital in overall job satisfaction. According to the findings of pre-observations and informal interviews conducted by Dekawati, I. et al. (2021) with several junior high school teachers in Brebes, Indonesia, it is known that some teachers still believe that several factors restrict their ability to engage in social activities together, particularly when conducting research, despite receiving adequate pay. There aren't many prospects for advancement in structural roles, and the help offered is scarce.

This perspective emphasizes that financial compensation and supportive environments that encourage collaboration and professional growth influence teacher satisfaction and engagement. Organizations that aim to enhance job satisfaction should consider sustaining and effectively engaging in extrinsic motivation to foster a more satisfied and productive workforce.

Table 4. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of Job Satisfaction

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
Item 13	I am satisfied with my current salary as a non-tenured teacher.	0.873	Job Satisfaction
Item 15	The compensation I receive reflects my level of experience and contribution.	0.851	
Item 14	My benefits package adequately meets my needs.	0.849	
Item 12	The job demands are reasonable for a non-tenured teacher.	0.753	
Item 18	The possibility of receiving tenure influences my motivation at work	0.609	
Item 1	I feel satisfied with my current teaching position.	0.588	
Item 10	My current workload is manageable	0.546	

Challenges and Influences. Table 5 shows challenges and influences as attribute components. There are five (5) items under these attributes. Item 21 focuses on uncertainties in future career progression due to a non-tenured status with a factor score of 0.805, which is the highest. In Item 20, the data shows a factor score of 0.735, which focuses on staying in the career as an educator due to no option for another job. Item 30, with a factor score of 0.659, indicates that the lack of tenure undermines motivation to remain in the current position. Item 27 shows that hiring in an organization is backed up by people known in the institution, with a factor score of 0.555. Finally, in item 22, the data shows that not feeling overwhelmed by administrative tasks is evident with a factor score of 0.554.

Teachers without tenure experience job instability, which leads to performance pressure and a reliance on outside incentives like pay, recognition, and job security. Due to their lack of tenure, they are more susceptible to outside influences that may demotivate them, especially if they believe that performance reviews and pay are unjust. These extrinsic difficulties might weaken intrinsic motivation, such as a deep love of teaching, which lowers engagement and work satisfaction.

Despite the presence of job instability, the provision of support for performance improvement can still lead to observable enhancements in performance outcomes. In a recent working paper published by the National Bureau of Economic Research, Eric Taylor, an associate professor of education at Harvard Graduate School of Education, where he looked at the effects of Tennessee's new tenure requirements and performance measures on teachers' job performance (2023, April 23). He concentrated on early-career public school teachers in Tennessee who instructed fourth- through eighth-grade students in arithmetic or English language arts. According to Taylor's findings, the new assessment scheme in Tennessee benefited the early careers of all teachers by having their administrators rate them during classroom observations and in other ways. However, teachers without tenure anticipated the future tenure requirements and experienced performance gains twice as substantial as those of teachers who had already earned tenure.

Table 5: Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of Challenges and Influences

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
Item 21	I feel uncertain about my future career progression due to my non-tenured status	0.805	Challenges and Influences
Item 20	I stayed in my career as an educator because I had no option for other careers	0.735	
Item 30	The lack of tenure negatively impacts my motivation to stay in my current position	0.659	
Item 27	I am hired because I know people from the institution (backer system)	0.555	
Item 22	I do not feel overwhelmed by administrative tasks (e.g., reports, paperwork, etc.)	0.554	

Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability. Table 6 shows the Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability attributes of this group. Both items have the same factor score of 0.601. Items 23 and 6 show that the number of students handled is appropriate for teaching and learning and that non-tenured teachers can access the resources needed to perform the job effectively.

The availability of essential resources and manageable workloads closely connect to the effectiveness of job performance in teaching. Non-tenured teachers face unique challenges that can significantly impact their ability to perform optimally, especially regarding class size and resource adequacy. These resources include instructional materials, technology, and support services, enabling teachers to effectively deliver lessons and support student engagement. When teachers have access to the right tools and materials, they can focus more on teaching than on the logistical challenges of accessing necessary resources.

In his study, Bizimana (2024) found an important positive impact between the availability of teaching resources and teachers' effectiveness in classroom management and the delivery of instructions. This study indicated that teachers were better equipped to manage classrooms effectively and deliver content proficiently when educational resources were adequately available. The results showed that a lack of resources in Huye District, Rwanda, made classroom management and content delivery more difficult. However, despite some mixed findings about the adequacy of resources, the study showed that despite limited resources, there was still a favorable connection between the availability of teaching materials and the quality of classroom management and content delivery.

Table 6. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
Item 23	The number of students I handle is appropriate for teaching and learning.	0.601	Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability
Item 6	I have access to the resources I need to perform my job effectively.	0.601	

Impact of Student Behavior and Workload. Table 7 presents the impact of student behavior and workload, with item no. 26 showing the highest factor score of 0.708, indicating that student behavior—whether positive or negative—significantly influences teaching motivation. Item 11 highlights non-tenured teachers' overwhelming workload and suggests that the required work often burdens them.

Student behavior shapes teaching quality, educator effectiveness, and overall classroom dynamics, particularly for non-tenured teachers. Disruptive or challenging behaviors can create significant barriers for teachers, impacting their ability to deliver effective instruction and maintain a productive learning environment.

Whalen (2023) observes that the regularity and intensity of behavioral challenges in the classroom have steadily increased, leaving many teachers needing more preparation to address these issues. Problematic behaviors, including bullying, tantrums, defiance, absconding, self-harm, combativeness, emotional outbursts, unresponsiveness, and non-compliance, are becoming more dominant. In Whalen's study, Prothero stated that over 70% of teachers reported a rise in disruptive classroom behavior, a notable increase from 66% in 2019.

Table 7. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of Impact of Student Behavior and Workload

Item No.	Attributes	Factor Score	Dimension
Item 26	Students behavior (positive or negative) affects my motivation to teach	0.708	Impact of Student Behavior and Workload
Item 11	I feel overwhelmed by the amount of work I have to complete.	0.532	

Framework Developed Based on the Findings

Job Fulfillment and Motivation. These are pivotal aspects of the teaching profession, influencing teachers' overall job satisfaction, retention, and effectiveness in the classroom. Job fulfillment refers to the satisfaction or

contentment teachers feel when their personal and professional needs are met through their work. Conversely, motivation is the internal drive that pushes teachers to achieve their professional goals, maintain enthusiasm, and enhance their teaching practice (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011).

Job Satisfaction. Overall satisfaction with one's teaching position is a composite measure influenced by compensation, job demands, and potential career progression. Teachers who are satisfied with their positions typically report a supportive work environment, fair evaluation practices, and growth opportunities (Dinham & Scott, 2000). Job satisfaction correlates strongly with lower attrition rates and higher student performance (Sass et al., 2012). For non-tenured teachers, feeling appreciated and supported enhances job satisfaction (Day & Gu, 2010).

Challenges and Influences. Non-tenured teachers often experience uncertainty regarding their future career progression. This lack of job security can contribute to elevated stress levels and impact motivation negatively (Ingersoll, 2001). Research highlights that job insecurity is one of the main stressors for educators, leading to anxiety and reduced commitment to their roles (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011). Non-tenured teachers may struggle to invest fully in their positions due to fears of job loss or limited career advancement opportunities (Borman & Dowling, 2008).

Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability. The number of students that teachers handle directly affects their ability to deliver quality instruction. Research indicates that smaller class sizes contribute to more individualized attention, better student engagement, and improved academic outcomes (Finn et al., 2001). Teachers in classrooms with manageable student-teacher ratios report higher job satisfaction and effectiveness in their teaching methods (Blatchford et al., 2011). The impact is particularly significant in lower-income schools where student needs may be greater (Rivkin et al., 2005). For non-tenured teachers, appropriate class sizes can reduce stress and provide an environment conducive to developing their teaching skills (Rockoff, 2004).

Impact of Student Behavior and Workload. Positive student behavior, such as enthusiasm, respect, engagement, and curiosity, plays a crucial role in fostering a supportive and motivating teaching environment. When students exhibit good behavior, it not only creates a productive classroom atmosphere but also positively influences the teacher's emotional well-being and motivation to teach. Teachers tend to feel more confident, appreciated, and energized, which enhances their teaching effectiveness.

Research has consistently shown that positive student behavior can lead to higher teacher satisfaction and a sense of professional accomplishment. For instance, studies by Hattie (2009) and Pianta et al. (2012) emphasize that a classroom characterized by respectful behavior, active participation, and cooperation increases teachers' motivation to remain committed to their work. Teachers who perceive their students as respectful and actively engaged report higher levels of self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

Figure 2. Work Motivation Framework of the Non-tenured Teachers

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SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of the findings and conclusions of the study. This also includes recommendations for different stakeholders.

SUMMARY

This quantitative study identified the factors that affect non-tenured teachers' job satisfaction and involvement. The factors that made the non-tenured teachers feel motivated and have a sincere love of teaching, which improves their professional growth and classroom engagement. A thirty-item survey questionnaire was given to one hundred fifty (150) respondents from the province of Davao del Sur.

The results of the KMO Test indicate that the KMO value is 0.826 surpassing the suggested value of 0.5. As can be seen, a KMO score above 0.8 is regarded as outstanding, this suggests that the sample is suitable and sufficient for factor analysis. Meanwhile, Bartlett's test demonstrated that the p-value is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming the presence of underlying components by showing that the correlation matrix differs significantly from the identity matrix. Applying the Eigenvalue criterion, it appears that the 30 items of the scale assess five underlying factors, as the first five components exhibit an Eigenvalue of 1 or above.

The findings of the study revealed five significant factors that made the non-tenured teachers feel motivated: Job Fulfillment and Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Challenges and Influences, Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability, and Impact of Student Behavior and Workload.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that there are five factors of the model that made the non-tenured teachers feel motivated. These are Job Fulfillment and Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Challenges and Influences, Teaching Conditions and Resource Availability, and Impact of Student Behavior and Workload.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusions discussed above, the following recommendations are formulated:

The **Department of Education (DepEd)** may utilize this model to direct the creation of programs and interventions to help improve and motivate non-tenured teachers.

The **Local and Provincial School Board** should make use of this model, prioritizing projects and solutions that support the improvement in teaching and increasing the benefits to be received by the non-tenured teachers, such as fair salary, employment security, performance reviews, and other extrinsic rewards.

Non-tenured teachers may use this model to guide how they can be more motivated than non-tenured teachers in public/private schools. It may help the non-tenured teachers to stay dedicated to the success of their profession, advance their careers, and feel appreciated, which improves retention and general well-being

Future researchers may use the result of the study as baseline information for future research attempts that investigate the work motivation of non-tenured teachers in various professional settings and fields. The work motivation framework built in this study can serve as a foundation for researchers to build upon to analyze other elements and variables that influence the capacity of professionals to deal with various challenges.

Furthermore, the approaches utilized in this study, such as Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), can serve as a model for doing research of a similar nature in other locations and industries. Through broadening the area of their investigation, future researchers will be able to contribute to a more thorough knowledge of resilience and the consequences it has for the well-being of the workforce as well as the dynamics of organizations.

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